

USE OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Abstract

Language is the manifestation of the existence of every nation, and its national wealth who lives in different parts of the world, the language factor is characterized as a unique phenomenon where the nation's historical culture and other unique characteristics are combined into a single complex.

The importance of project-based learning is kind of approach in which students try to solve the problems they may encounter in their lives within the framework of a scenario by connecting with different disciplines in the classroom environment and in real life. This method is organizing the educational process, excludes the traditional principles of planning and arranging trainings. When implementing a project, it is necessary to follow a sequence of concrete actions to achieve a certain goal. The method of projects, as we know, always assumes the existence of a problem of either subjective or social importance. In addition, the project method is always pragmatic by its nature: it includes not only the review, study of the identified problem, the search for its solutions, but also the practical implementation of the results obtained in a specific activity product.

Keywords: project, method, students, problem, plan, cognitive

Introduction

A project is a set of actions specially organized by the teacher and independently carried out by students, culminating in the creation of a creative product.

The project based learning is set of educational and cognitive techniques that allow solving a particular problem as a result of independent actions of students with the obligatory presentation of these results.

The project method always involves solving a problem, which involves, on the one hand, the use of various methods, and on the other hand, the integration of knowledge and skills from various fields of science, engineering, technology, and creative fields. (6. p 69)

The project method is based on the development of students' cognitive skills, the ability to independently construct their knowledge, the ability to navigate the information space, and the development of critical thinking.

Working according to the project method presupposes not only the presence and awareness of a problem, but also the process of revealing it and solving it, which includes clear planning of actions, the presence of an idea or hypothesis for solving this problem, a clear distribution

(in group work) of roles, and etc. It tasks for each participant, subject to close interaction.

The project method is used when any research or creative task arises in the educational process, the solution of which requires integrated knowledge from various fields, as well as the use of research techniques.

Methodology

Methodological projects were developed at the beginning of the 20th century with the aim of orienting education towards the expedient activities of children, taking into account their personal interests. Having come up with his so-called method of problems, the teacher connected it with the ideas of the humanistic direction in the field of philosophy and education.

Recently, this method has again received close attention in many countries around the world. This is an educational methodology in which the center is the student, and the goal is to make him independent, creative and proactive. A student or schoolchild develops these qualities through his own actions while studying interesting and meaningful topics.

Main part

The main idea of the project method is the focus of schoolchildren's educational and cognitive activity on the result that is obtained when solving a practical or theoretical problem. This result is called a project, which in translation means a plan. Project is understood as a well-founded, planned and conscious activity aimed at developing in schoolchildren a certain system of intellectual and practical skills. The technology for organizing schoolchildren's project activities includes a set of research, search and problem-based methods, creative in their essence aim the student's independent implementation of the intended result. (11, p 21)

Project based learning is problematic in lower grades because children are still too young to design. We will talk about presenting only elements of project activity in the classical sense. But this will be a project that the student can do himself. Savenkov A.I. believes that the practice of conducting pedagogical research with elementary school students can be considered a special field of extracurricular work, which is closely related to the main educational process and is aimed at the development and deepening of research and creative activity of children. and strengthen existing knowledge, skills and abilities. This work can be carried out individually, with a small group of children and during the main educational activity [36, p 45). The project and research activities belong to the field of children's independence, are based on the interests of schoolchildren, satisfy them and therefore personality-oriented for each child. The special importance of design and research activity in primary school is that in its

process they get social experience outside of school and adapt to modern life conditions. The following types of projects can be organized within the framework of classroom and extracurricular activities in primary school.:

1. Purpose, goals, tasks, main idea, approximate topics and forms of the future project.
2. Poster information about the project.
3. Providing recommendations to future authors (topics, requirements, deadlines, etc.).
4. Consultations on the selection of topics for educational projects, the formation of ideas and plans.
5. Formation of groups.
6. Approval of projects' topics and duration of work on them.
7. Search phase.
8. Consultations on the content and design of projects.
9. Generalization stage: presentation of results.
10. Finalization of projects taking into account comments and suggestions.

11. Preparation for public defense of the project.
12. Final stage: public defense of the project.
13. Summarizing and analyzing the work done.
14. The final stage. Summary of materials.

Project activity of students is a joint educational, cognitive, creative or gaming activity that has a common goal, agreed upon methods, plans of activity, aimed at achieving a common result. An indispensable condition for project activity is the presence of pre-developed ideas about its final product and, as a consequence, about the stages of design and implementation of the project, including its comprehension of the results of the activity. The possibilities of the project method for the development of personality and the socialization of schoolchildren are identified through an analysis of the structure of the activities of the teacher and the student, which differs significantly from the structure of their activities in the traditional organization of training.

(13, p 68)

This structure can be represented as follows:

The project-based methodology in teaching a foreign language allows each of student to create deeper environment for communication, which contributes better mastery and the successful solution of emerging language difficulties.

There some types of projects for students such as:

. **Research.** Such a project is as close as possible to scientific work. It must have a clear structure and define the object, subject, goals and objectives of the study. It is also necessary to explain why the problem chosen for the research work is really relevant.

. **Informational.** As the name suggests, the main thing in such a project is the ability to work with

information. It needs to be found in different sources and analyzed conclusions.

. **Practice-oriented.** The structure is similar to a research type, but the result should be something applied, that is, something that can be used in a certain activity. For example: a measuring device or a series of lectures for junior classes.

. **Creative.** Here, nothing limits the authors of the project in choosing the method of its implementation. For example, you can make a film, , give a lecture, organize a holiday or an environmental campaign.

. **Role-playing game.** A group of authors assign roles among themselves, and the result is usually a presentation. During the performance, its characters

answer a problematic question or find a solution. A convenient format for working with the whole class. Educational projects at school can be individual or group. Each student works alone on an individual project. A group can have several participants. Some projects are prepared as a whole class.

Findings

Teachers can choose different topics for project. In some cases, this topic can be formulated by specialists from educational authorities within the framework of approved programs. In others, teachers can take the initiative, taking into account the educational situation in their subject, natural professional interests, interests and abilities of students. Project based learning is learning technology of the future. It can be actively implemented both in class and in extracurricular activities of students. This technology allows each student to independently gain experience in research and practical activities, broaden their horizons and expand their active and passive

vocabulary. Project-based learning technology also develops in students various practical skills that they need so much in future life, such as searching for and working with information, and the ability not only to express their point of view, but also to argue for their answer.

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